

ATTACHABLE IOT-BASED DIGITAL TWIN FRAMEWORK SPECIALIZED FOR SME PRODUCTION LINES

Kang, B. G. * & Kim, B. S. **.#

* Korea National Industrial Convergence Center, Korea Institute of Industrial Technology,
15588, Ansan, Republic of Korea

** Dept. of Applied Artificial Intelligence, Seoul National University of Science and Technology,
01811, Seoul, Republic of Korea

E-Mail: bkgang@kitech.re.kr, bskim@seoultech.ac.kr (# Corresponding author)

Abstract

While large enterprises are actively preparing for digital transformation by leveraging technologies such as digital twins, smaller companies face challenges due to economic constraints and market uncertainties, leading to a relative lack of awareness and readiness. To address this situation, this study proposes a digital twin development framework tailored for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). This framework utilizes attachable IoT devices for real-time collection of manufacturing data and leverages public server systems for data management. Moreover, it enables the refinement and optimization of digital twins by training machine learning models on collected data. Additionally, the framework includes the integration of simulation models and machine learning models for comprehensive digital twin modelling. Finally, the paper suggests a process for applying and validating this framework in real manufacturing companies, demonstrating the effects of digital twin implementation on productivity enhancement in the production lines of two SMEs.

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Key Words: Digital Twin, IoT Device, Modelling and Simulation, Production Line, Small and Medium-Sized Enterprise

1. INTRODUCTION

In the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, many manufacturing companies are pursuing digital transformation (DX) to increase efficiency, competitiveness, and reduce costs alongside the transition of manufacturing paradigms [1]. While large enterprises are preparing for DX, although not fully, the awareness and readiness for DX among SMEs remain considerably inadequate [2]. Unlike large corporations, SMEs face considerable difficulties due to economic constraints and market uncertainties. To adapt to rapidly changing business environments and diverse customer demands, DX is deemed essential [3]. Various methods such as establishing smart factories, expanding online businesses, adopting cloud computing, and implementing remote management can be utilized to achieve DX [4]. Particularly, technologies that enable rapid and flexible responses to frequently changing requirements and urgently responsive production are necessary to enhance SME productivity [5].

Among these methods, one approach involves building and utilizing digital twins of actual systems to predict and optimize processes [6]. A digital twin is a digital model that faithfully simulates physical objects, enabling the resolution of various real-world problems [7]. Constructing such digital twins involves utilizing various ICT tools and ensuring organic integration of data processing, modelling and simulation, 3D visualization, and networking technologies to create comprehensive digital twins [8, 9]. Furthermore, manufacturing big data management and analysis are conducted based on cloud platforms, establishing digital twin systems synchronized with the field, which in turn achieve operations, visualization, knowledge management, and optimization [10].

In particular, to build advanced digital twins, the data, terrain/space/shape, function/behaviour, etc. of the actual system must be selected and copied according to the

purpose. It can be modelled by duplicating a single aspect or combining various parts. It is also important to build a digital twin by acquiring data from the real world [11]. This increases the accuracy of the digital twin, creates a more realistic model, and allows it to predict and respond to problems that will occur in the actual field [12].

Many SMEs, facing challenges such as low skill levels and inefficient line designs, encounter difficulties in securing production volume. Hence, there is a need to explore productivity enhancement through digital twin construction [13]. However, SMEs may exhibit reluctance or resistance to invest in such endeavours due to uncertainties regarding immediate efficiency improvements. Additionally, the lack of up-to-date equipment, relevant experts, and established information systems poses obstacles to constructing advanced digital twins [14]. Particularly, in cases involving outdated equipment or manual processes, real-time data acquisition during production may be challenging, limiting the quality of digital twin construction. Moreover, many lack the necessary data infrastructure for collecting, processing, and transmitting such data. Additionally, the absence of specialized personnel in areas such as digital twins, simulation, and artificial intelligence complicates the practical application of DX initiatives, despite intentions to do so. Consequently, there is a need for a support process tailored to SMEs that enables the practical implementation of digital twins. Although national efforts are underway to support SMEs in executing DX initiatives, a specialized framework for digital twin construction remains absent [15].

Therefore, this study aims to research a digital twin construction framework tailored to SMEs. This framework facilitates real-time manufacturing data collection using attached IoT devices, enables advanced digital twin development through data management on public servers and machine learning model training, and achieves digital twin completion through the fusion of simulation modelling and machine learning models. Moreover, this study proposes a digital twin construction process through collaboration among digital twin experts, public support agencies, and demand-side institutions. It applies and demonstrates the proposed framework and process to two actual SMEs: a mask manufacturing line facing difficulties in securing production volume post-COVID-19 and a food processing line. This aims to validate the applicability and effectiveness of the proposed framework and process in real SME settings. Finally, this paper aims to contribute to the productivity enhancement of SMEs by proposing an overall support framework (including devices, modelling processes, infrastructure, etc.) that enables the utilization of digital twins, which are often challenging for SMEs to establish.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 covers the literature review and section 3 proposes an attachable IoT-based digital twin construction framework. Then, section 4 presents case studies that applies the proposed framework to manufacturing lines of SMEs. Finally, section 5 concludes the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital twins can be constructed not as a singular technology but through the convergence of various ICTs such as simulation, data analytics, machine learning, IoT, and networking. In other words, achieving a true digital twin requires synergy arising from the integration of different technologies, rather than utilizing each technology independently. To build such digital twins, various consideration points need to be taken into account, including data collection and processing, digital twin modelling, 3D visualization, and interfaces [16].

In relation to this, numerous studies exist on the construction of digital twins. Methodologies [17, 18] and frameworks [19, 20] for manufacturing digital twin construction are actively being developed. Particularly, comprehensive frameworks for digital twin construction mainly assume the establishment of various infrastructures necessary for digital twins in manufacturing lines. Studies often assume the utilization of sensors and data collection

infrastructures embedded in high-cost equipment and facilities, which may be difficult for SMEs to adopt [21, 22]. Furthermore, many studies propose concepts rather than practical methods applicable to SMEs, leading to challenges in actual utilization.

Moreover, many large enterprises are independently constructing smart factories, including digital twins, to enhance productivity [23], possessing sufficient research and development capabilities and infrastructures for their construction and operation. They are leading in activating manufacturing digital twins by organically integrating existing systems such as Business & Market Strategy Systems (ERP/PIMS/RPMS), Production Management Systems (DCS/MES/LIMS), and various Industrial Automation Systems for simulating and optimizing systems [24].

Through such research, it is possible to construct high-level, high-performance digital twins that can be integrated with various legacy systems to gain new insights and build large-scale models. However, due to the significant manpower, time, and cost required for comprehensive digital construction, it is practically challenging for SMEs to adopt them directly. Specifically, it is difficult for SMEs to approach and apply digital twins unless they are of a medium-sized scale or larger, possess advanced facilities capable of self-data collection, have established MES for data collection and management, and have relevant personnel. Therefore, there is a need for a digital twin construction framework specialized for SME production lines. While various studies exist analysing the application of digital twins in small and medium-sized manufacturing companies [13, 25-27], they are all one-time analyses, and there is no universally applicable support framework.

3. PROPOSED DIGITAL TWIN FRAMEWORK FOR SMES

This study focuses on researching a digital twin construction support framework and collaboration process specialized for SMEs, distinct from large enterprises with structured infrastructures and construction systems as depicted in Fig. 1. In particular, designing attached IoT devices makes them easily applicable to SMEs' manual or outdated equipment, ensuring easy data acquisition and high reusability. Moreover, embedding pre-processing units within these devices facilitates the extraction of meaningful data from acquired data, simplifying data processing. Additionally, leveraging support infrastructure, experts, and highly reusable devices can minimize the costs of digital twin construction. Furthermore, utilizing the completed digital twin model facilitates the analysis and improvement of production lines. Improved parameters based on optimization results are communicated to both the devices and operators, aiding decision-making to eliminate inefficiencies and enhance production line productivity.

Figure 1: Conceptual difference of proposed work.

To support the construction of digital twin models for SMEs, it is essential to establish organic collaboration among the supporting institution (public institution), the demand-side institution (SMEs), and digital twin experts. Fig. 2 illustrates the roles that each of these three institutions must perform for digital twin construction.

Figure 2: Diagram of the alliance of three organizations for the digital twin support.

Firstly, the public institution is responsible for overall management of SME support, securing funding for supporting SMEs, and utilizing it to establish and maintain actual infrastructure and IoT platforms. Additionally, the public institution selects SMEs for support, matches them with digital twin experts, and conducts pre-arrangements and consultations. During this process, SMEs, along with digital twin experts, identify requirements and perform overall conceptual modelling. Subsequently, through requirement analysis, the public institution selects data types, sensors, etc., designs IoT devices, and digital twin experts perform digital twin modelling. Then, after securing actual data from SMEs and integrating it into the digital twin model, an optimized model is derived, and improvements are made based on SME feedback. SMEs aim to enhance operational efficiency and productivity in the field by applying the digital twin model. During this process, the public institution provides computing resource support and post-support for a certain period, and utilizing the established infrastructure and IoT platform, continuous support for digital twin construction for various small and medium-sized manufacturing companies is possible in the long term.

To execute the aforementioned process, this chapter proposes an attachable IoT platform based digital twin construction framework. The proposed framework consists of attachable IoT device, digital twin modelling, and infrastructure, as depicted in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Overall structure of proposed work.

3.1 Attachable IoT platform

To enhance the sophistication of digital twin models or ensure real-time data availability for models, acquisition of real-time operational process data from the production line is necessary. To achieve this, an attachable IoT device is constructed for data collection and integration, enabling real-time data collection from the line.

This device comprises multi-sensors for attachment/ installation on manufacturing equipment and lines to collect data, a data preprocessor to preprocess/process them for utilization in actual digital twin models, and a communication module (interface) to transmit/receive processed data to/from the analysis system via networks. Additionally, components such as embedded controller modules with displays, (vibration measurement) data acquisition (DAQ) modules, micro controller units (MCUs), and user interface for data monitoring and control are included. This device is designed with scalability to enable diverse data acquisition and preprocessing through various types of sensors in the future. The sensors of this device can be attached to existing equipment, manual operations, etc., to acquire data, which can be utilized diversely for the advancement of digital twin models. For instance, as depicted below in Fig. 4, noise/vibration data can be acquired and processed to secure significant operating cycles, or transformed using techniques like Fast Fourier Transform (FFT).

Figure 4: Components of attachable IoT platform.

Among the pre-processed data, patterns of time-series data such as operating cycles can be learned to predict operating times and identify fluctuation trends. Additionally, FFT-transformed vibration patterns can be utilized to train equipment fault diagnosis (predictive) models. Moreover, real-time images of the line can be acquired using image sensors and utilized to train models for worker behaviour analysis and safety prediction.

3.2 Digital twin modelling

The following is the abstraction and application of manufacturing process/line through digital twin modelling of the manufacturing line. Digital twin modelling can be achieved through the convergence of theory/knowledge-based traditional simulation modelling methods and data-driven modelling methods [28]. The simulation modelling is a theory-based approach based on abstraction of the system using physical/operational knowledge which is generally used when sufficient information related to the system can be secured [29]. Especially in the manufacturing field, modelling can be performed by using various commercial solutions such as Plant Simulation, Visual Component, AnyLogic, or by directly using the discrete event system specification (DEVS) formalism, etc. Also, data modelling is based on analysing the data of a system, in particular finding connections between the system state variables without explicit knowledge of the system behaviour, which is mainly used when there is sufficient data that can be collected through the operation of the target system [29].

In the case of a typical manufacturing line, digital twin modelling is possible by dividing the structural model that contains the manufacturing logic and the parameters/functions that determine specific values. This is done by embedding the machine learning model that determines the parameters/functions in the system’s structural model. As Fig. 5 shows, a structural model is first established for modelling the manufacturing line, and its validation problem can be solved through data modelling [30]. Specifically, the structural model of the system is modelled using models such as DEVS model, and the parameters and transition functions required for the structural model are learned using data obtained from operation of real manufacturing line and elements of machine learning, such as artificial neural networks. At this time, the entire model can be completed by applying the learned and validated parameters and transfer functions to the structural model. In Summary, sensor data, depending on the purpose, can be refined through sensor fusion to be reflected in the form of real-time parameters of the digital twin model [31]. Through this, it is possible to solve the validation problem of simulation modelling and the limitation of structural change of data modelling simultaneously.

Figure 5: Detailed digital twin modelling process.

3.3 Digital twin infrastructure

The following describes the overall infrastructure, including a general-purpose server system capable of managing SME facility data. In this paper, to ensure stable operation under data collection conditions from various SME, we divided the server system into three major categories: 1) data integration system, 2) data storage/management system, and 3) data monitoring/analysis system, as depicted in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Detailed components of digital twin infrastructure.

First, the data integration system receives and preprocesses data generated from IoT devices, and then delivers it to the data storage/management system. Because IoT devices and this system exist in physically different locations, a communication interface environment for them is provided. After first performing an integrity check on the data received through this, it is classified or combined according to the data type, and it delivered the data to the data storage/management system periodically or as an event according to the batch schedule.

Second, the data storage/management system performs the role of converting data received from the data integration system into a database and providing it to the monitoring/analysis system. We built an environment where the DB table configuration can be changed so that different data types can be stored and managed depending on the small and medium-sized business. A Web Application Server with data management and statistical analysis functions was built to maintain the DB, and it was implemented separately to allow access by small and medium-sized business users and administrator levels. In addition, to ensure data management stability for the system, a dual server environment was established, not only in terms of software but also physically.

Lastly, the data monitoring/analysis system provides various small and medium-sized managers and users with an environment where they can monitor and analyse data in the storage/management system in real-time. The system provides complete and detailed data inquiries, statistical analyses of the searched data, visualization in graph form, and file storage and upload functions. It consists of a dashboard-type web application, and different dashboard access rights are granted to each user to prevent access to other companies' data. The web application provides an advanced artificial intelligence analysis environment by connecting with its deep learning server and provides an interworking environment with the digital twin model through connection to an external communication interface.

4. APPLICATIONS

In this chapter, the proposed research is applied to two SMEs engaged in mask manufacturing and food production, respectively. This demonstrates how the proposed research can be applied to real SMEs and the effects it can bring.

4.1 Facial mask production line

In the era of COVID-19, the sharp increase in demand for masks necessitated an expansion in production capacity by mask manufacturing companies. However, most mask production is carried out by SMEs, which faced difficulties in securing production volumes due to factors such as low skill levels of workers, challenges in equipment procurement, and cost burdens. Therefore, to increase production volume without additional deployment of production equipment, analysis and efficiency improvement of the line using digital twin technology are necessary.

However, due to the limitations of SMEs as described earlier, DX is practically difficult. Thus, digital twin construction for the mask production line is achieved using the proposed framework. The overall outline of digital twin construction for the mask production line is depicted in Fig. 7. Firstly, the manufacturing process/line is analysed, and a simulation model of the production line is built through abstraction and modelling. Siemens Plant Simulation software was utilized for modelling. Additionally, IoT sensors are attached to cutting equipment and strap attachment devices to collect real-time data from the equipment. Real-time vibration data from the cutting equipment were obtained, pre-processed to secure real-time operating times, and then reflected in real-time synchronization with the digital twin model at the site through the server of the constructed infrastructure. This model not only facilitates real-time monitoring but also predicts daily production volumes in advance.

Figure 7: Process of applying the proposed work to the mask manufacturing line.

Furthermore, to improve the capacity and line of balance (LOB) of the manufacturing line, as shown in Fig. 8, simulation-based optimization was performed using a completed model applied with on-site data. Specifically, by conducting distributed simulations, improvements were made by altering the form of parallel work cells, determining the optimal buffer length and structure, and rearranging the process layout to derive the optimal production quantity and LOB. These improvements were then applied to the actual mask manufacturing line, leading to an 8% increase in actual daily production. In essence, through the proposed support process, inefficiencies in the line and process were eliminated, confirming the possibility of optimizing process parameters, job scheduling, and line structure.

Figure 8: Result of applying the proposed work.

Finally, vibration data from the cutting process was automatically pre-processed to obtain time-series pattern data suitable for machine learning. This data was then utilized to train a model capable of detecting defects in the process (or abnormalities in the equipment) in advance. However, due to the unavailability of data during process defects, meaningful model training was not feasible in this case study. Instead, only the potential of such modelling was confirmed through verification of interface operation.

4.2 Food production line

Food processing companies require accurate production planning for timely deliveries, but they represent one of the SME sectors with poor digital transformation. Moreover, complete automation is difficult, necessitating manual labour and resulting in irregular production volumes. Additionally, demand frequently fluctuates due to seasonal menus and orders from customers, leading to inefficiencies in worker deployment. Therefore, due to the suitability of applying the proposed framework, a case study is conducted targeting a meat processing company.

Meat processing is broadly divided into primary processing, meat cutting processes, portioning processes, thermoforming, inspection processes, and box packaging, as shown in Fig. 9. Automated processes generally have consistent work times, but manual portioning processes vary in work times depending on skill levels. That is, if skill levels are low, not only do work times increase, but the variance in work times also becomes larger. Up to 8 workers can be assigned to the portioning process, and analysis is needed to determine the minimum number of workers required to achieve the target production volume and how many skilled workers are needed among them. (Analysis is also needed to determine the production volume based on the ratio of skilled workers to beginners if beginners need to fill in when skilled workers have gaps in work.) Furthermore, since workloads may vary depending on the location of workers, optimal work assignments are necessary to ensure maximum production volume.

Figure 9: Food production process and its digital twin.

Therefore, in this case study, IoT devices are used to obtain real-time work times, averages, and standard deviations for the portioning process, which are then applied to the digital twin model of food processing. Subsequently, using the completed digital twin model, simulation-based optimization is performed to determine the optimal worker deployment for achieving the target production volume. Fig. 9 illustrates the actual food processing line, including the portioning process, and shows the digital twin model analysed from it. Similar to the first case study, Siemens Plant Simulation software was used for modelling.

Fig. 10 demonstrates the process and results of performing simulation-based optimization using the data obtained through IoT devices and experimental plans and applying them to the digital twin model. As evident from the experimental result graph, it is confirmed that with a minimum of 6 workers, including 4 skilled workers, the target production volume of 220 boxes can be achieved within the standard work time of 390 minutes. Thus, even if 2 skilled workers are replaced by beginners among the portioning workers, there is no disruption to achieving the target production volume. Additionally, with only 3 skilled workers, a total of 7 workers can achieve the target production volume. Furthermore, as shown in the lower right of Fig. 10, more work is performed towards the latter part of the portioning line, and to maximize production, skilled workers should be placed in the latter part. Finally, by finding the optimal conditions (4 skilled workers and 2 beginners) to meet the daily target production, we were able to achieve a 15.8 % reduction in labour costs compared to the existing operating line. Moreover, optimization can be conducted by changing the layout of the food factory, including the deployment of workers in the thermoforming process, based on the fluctuating daily target production volumes characteristic of the work.

Figure 10: Experimental design and result.

4.3 Contribution and analysis

Introducing digital twin models to existing production lines of SMEs enhances production efficiency and enables the supply of competitive products at low prices. Particularly, it allows for increasing production volume without additional equipment or line expansions and enables efficient personnel management and cost reduction. Furthermore, by collecting and managing real-time information on major manufacturing processes and equipment operation conditions, it is possible to systematize manufacturing data management. Visualization and sharing of equipment operation rate information based on such data are also possible. Moreover, by detecting equipment failures in advance, it is possible to reduce downtime and increase operating rates, achieving the additional effect of collecting effective data generated in the factory in real-time through IoT environment construction. As many SMEs are seeking manufacturing innovation through digital transformation, the proposed digital twin framework can serve as an important tool for enhancing the competitiveness of SMEs in the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Additionally, by expanding the service scope in the manufacturing field through digital twin-based services, digital twin frameworks can be utilized to widen the service scope in manufacturing beyond production and equipment manufacturing.

5. CONCLUSION

In the manufacturing industry, digital twins play a crucial role as a technological enabler for manufacturing innovation. However, SMEs face challenges in adopting digital twins due to practical difficulties. To overcome this situation, this study proposes a digital twin construction framework tailored to SMEs in the manufacturing sector. This framework utilizes attachable IoT devices to collect real-time manufacturing data and employs a public server system to manage the data. The attachable IoT devices are designed for easy application to manual and aging equipment commonly found in SMEs, facilitating straightforward data acquisition and high reusability. Furthermore, the collected data is used to train machine learning models, enabling the enhancement and optimization of digital twins. The framework also includes digital twin modelling that integrates simulation and machine learning models.

In this paper, the feasibility of the proposed framework was validated through collaboration among digital twin experts, public support institutions, and actual demand-driven enterprises, conducting case studies targeting mask production lines and food processing lines. Through analysis of operational manufacturing lines, simulation models were constructed. IoT devices were attached to mask cutting and food processing equipment to collect operational data for model training, thereby refining the digital twin models. Ultimately, the developed digital twin models were utilized to propose improvements for each line, enhancing productivity through equipment and operational restructuring. Thus, it was confirmed that the proposed framework can improve production efficiency, streamline manpower utilization, and reduce costs within SMEs at minimal expense and in a short timeframe. This work provided a digital twin support

framework that enables SMEs, which have difficulty building a digital twin environment, to use digital twins, thereby contributing to improving the productivity of SMEs.

Since the analysis of the target companies was simplistic in this study, only vibration sensors and noise sensors were utilized to obtain basic data. Future research will focus on exploring sensor fusion technologies using various sensors such as image sensors to automatically acquire advanced, meaningful data. Additionally, the framework will be expanded to accommodate advanced scenarios such as fault diagnosis and safety prediction, with further research planned to apply these advancements to real SMEs.

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